

Journal of Metaphysical Thought Editor's Note

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Dear reader,

Thank you for taking the time to read this inaugural issue of the *Journal of Metaphysical Thought*. The concept for this journal came about due to the lack of modern peer reviewed publications that address “practical” metaphysics. There are, however, several professional journals that focus on metaphysics from a purely academic and philosophical perspective. The gap between this form of high-minded academic thought and the applied metaphysics practiced the world over is, to say the least, substantial. Academic metaphysics anchored in philosophical logic and reasoning, while useful in its own right, leaves little to no room for divine inspiration. From a practical metaphysics standpoint, it is the divine spark within us that awakens our inner wisdom and, when guided by our own intuition, makes metaphysical practice special and “unquantifiable.”

Modern metaphysics as practiced by mystics and spiritual seekers around the world often does not follow logic, nor is it bound by a reason-based understanding of the universe(s). As any student of meditation knows, wisdom and ideas come from within often when most needed to help us make sense of our lives and experiences. (Not necessarily when most needed to meet a publish-or-perish deadline.) Over time, with dedicated practice, a “big picture” spiritual understanding of life slowly emerges. “Going within” to answer life’s questions might seem counterintuitive to one dedicated to the life of the mind. And yet, metaphysical practices in their many forms have powerfully improved the lives of many.

And so, the separation arises: academic metaphysics anchored firmly in understanding life, consciousness, and God from a third-dimensional perspective anchored in logic and

reason versus practical and applied metaphysics guided by inner wisdom and intuition. For two fields that share the same name and overall purpose, they couldn’t be more different. Over time, the “ivory tower” has adopted the philosophical understanding of metaphysics, resigning practical and applied metaphysics to the fringe of human experience. This is, of course, nothing new in the grand scheme as mystics and spiritual seekers who “go against the grain” have often been quiet practitioners.

However, in this time of Aquarian awakening many practices and concepts once kept secret have gone mainstream. The Law of Attraction (just one of many universal laws), meditation, and mindfulness practices are great examples. Yet practical and applied metaphysics remains something deemed not quite “good enough” for traditional academia. That, too, is slowly changing as a new and old universities alike adopt metaphysical principles into their curricula. We may never see metaphysics properly regarded for its transformative power in our lifetimes, but for now we can trust that those who are destined to discover metaphysics now have ample opportunity to do so.

The *Journal of Metaphysical Thought* enters the picture to somewhat “bridge the gap” so to speak in mending the separation of theoretical and applied metaphysical fields in professional literature. Metaphysical practitioners need an avenue (multiple avenues, really) to share their work and perspectives, driven by that tiny but mighty divine spark, inner wisdom, and intuition. To share our work in a professional manner, we must adopt some of the practices established by traditional academic publishing. However, traditional academic publishing is plagued with challenges ranging from

counter-productive peer review processes to “pay-to-publish” schemes to outright falsification of data and research. (*And they call us “woo woo.”*) The examples are endless. And yet, some of these principles are good in theory. Every discipline needs benchmarks to ensure, encourage, and reward high quality work (while weeding out plagiarism and sloppy research).

To produce a high-quality publication, the *Journal of Metaphysical Thought* has adopted the following guidelines for the publication of articles. Authors are welcome to submit articles representing any theme that falls within metaphysics, consciousness studies, or New Thought (with or without a religious perspective). To account for the diversity of topics and needs, the Journal accepts research articles, “brief” articles, “practice-based” articles, case studies, reviews (of literature or books), and “perspective” articles (similar to guest editorials). Ideally each journal will contain a mix of these article types.

All articles submitted first go through a rigorous content-based editorial review. Those acceptable for inclusion in the journal are anonymized and referred for peer review. Unlike traditional journals, articles referred for peer review are already tentatively accepted for publication. Peer reviewers for our journal are not the arbiters of which articles will not be published (except in cases of plagiarism or something similar). Our peer reviewers focus on helping authors to make their articles stronger. Results from peer review are reviewed by the editor and anonymized comments are referred back to the author. Articles are accepted for final publication on the condition that the author makes revisions identified during peer review. This process avoids many of the issues rampant in traditional peer review.

The Journal has committed to produce two issues per year, though this may change depending on demand. As an “open access” publication, all work is made available free (no

registration required) via our website (www.metaphysicalthought.com). Unlike many other “open access” journals, we never charge authors a fee to submit their work. For those interested in print copies of the journal, printed issues of journals may be ordered online for a nominal fee.

We rely 100% on volunteers to edit, design, peer review, and write articles. As such, if after reading the journal you are interested in contributing some of your time to our cause, please feel free to contact the editor (editor@metaphysicalthought.com).

This issue contains articles from a variety of perspectives to provide a taste of what’s to come in future issues. Our next issue (December 2018) will be themed “metaphysical healing” and will include articles focusing on a wide spectrum of modern techniques. Full submission guidelines are available at www.metaphysicalthought.com.

I hope you enjoy this issue and I welcome your feedback. Thank you to the authors and peer reviewers for their hard work in bringing this issue to life and to members of the editorial board for their continued service to the Journal.

Sincerely,

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